

THE IMPACT OF FORAGE CROPS ON SOIL FERTILITY**F. Pulatov**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the impact of cultivating forage crops on soil fertility. The agro-technical characteristics of high-nutritional-value crop species and their effects on the composition and physico-chemical properties of soil have been studied. Furthermore, based on recent years' practices of growing these crops as primary or secondary (repeated) crops, their role in increasing the levels of humus, nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium in the soil has been determined. The research results highlight the importance of forage crops not only in the field of animal husbandry but also in ensuring agroecological sustainability. The article also presents practical recommendations for maintaining and improving soil fertility through the cultivation of forage crops.

Keywords: Forage crops, PAR (Photosynthetically Active Radiation), catch crop, green manure crop, green biomass, organic matter, stubble.

Uzbekistan's soil and climatic conditions, the expansion of grain crop areas in recent years, and the fact that agriculture is predominantly conducted under irrigated conditions indicate the potential for cultivating catch and repeated crops and obtaining high yields from them. This idea is also supported by theoretical calculations: in the central regions of the country, approximately 8 billion kcal of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) fall on one hectare of cropland

annually. Of this amount, 3.2 billion kcal of PAR is received during the vegetation period (April to August), while the remaining portion falls between September and March. The mild conditions of autumn, winter, and early spring are highly favorable for growing catch crops, which in turn allows for the cultivation of subsequent crops after their harvest.

Crop residues and root remains play an important role in enriching the soil with organic matter. Intermediate and green manure crops sown after winter wheat have been found to produce 28.8–30.63 tons/ha and 3.14–3.34 tons/ha of green biomass, respectively. When grown in rotation with wheat, intermediate crops enrich the soil by 7.64–7.79 tons/ha, while green manure crops combined with winter wheat contribute 37.44–38.86 tons/ha of organic matter to the soil [1].

If mungbean is sown after winter wheat in stubble fields using a special technology under limited irrigation conditions and within optimal sowing dates, it can yield 1.86–1.93 tons/ha of grain. This significantly increases the accumulation of natural nitrogen in the soil [3].

Among crops, alfalfa leaves the highest amount of residue in the soil. However, in current farming practices, even the cultivation of annual leguminous crops after winter wheat can positively maintain and support soil fertility [2].

In our study, the effects of forage crops and the subsequent cultivation of soybean on soil nutrient content were investigated. In the 1st and 2nd variants of the experiment, where no intermediate forage crops were sown and maize and soybean were cultivated in the following years, the amount of nitrate nitrogen in the 0–30 cm and 30–50 cm soil layers initially amounted to 9.1–8.9 mg/kg and 6.2–6.3 mg/kg, respectively. By the end of the growing season, these indicators were found to be 8.5–18.3 mg/kg and 6.7–10.5 mg/kg, respectively.

This means that after maize, the nitrate nitrogen content in the 0–30 cm layer decreased by 0.6 mg/kg compared to the initial level, while after soybean, it increased by 9.7 mg/kg. This indicates that soybean plants, through the activity of

nodule bacteria, contribute to an increase in the nitrogen content of the soil.

In variants 3 and 4, where forage crops such as mustard and barley were sown, the nitrate nitrogen content in the 0–30 cm soil layer was 13.6–15.5 mg/kg in the first year and 21.5–21.7 mg/kg in the second year. By the end of the growing season, these values had decreased to 8.1–9.1 mg/kg and 13.2–9.2 mg/kg, respectively. This decrease is attributed to the nutrient uptake patterns of these crops. After harvesting these forage crops, soybean was sown, and by the end of its growing season, the nitrate nitrogen content reached 20.5–20.4 mg/kg and 36.3–38.0 mg/kg, respectively. This confirms an increase in nitrate nitrogen levels following soybean cultivation.

In variant 5, where a mixture of two-component forage crops (triticale + rapeseed) was sown, the initial nitrate nitrogen content in the 0–30 cm soil layer was 12.8 mg/kg in the first year and increased to 23.8 mg/kg in the second year. These values decreased to 7.8–5.0 mg/kg by the end of the growing season, but rose again to 19.0 and 39.0 mg/kg, respectively, after the cultivation of soybean.

In the variants where forage crops were sown as three- and four-component mixtures, a decrease in nitrate nitrogen content was observed by the end of the growing period compared to the initial values. However, this content increased again after soybean cultivation. Relatively favorable results were observed in variant 8 (triticale + rapeseed + pea + radish), where the initial nitrate nitrogen content was 12.6 mg/kg, decreased to 6.3 mg/kg by the end of the forage crop growing period, and then increased to 14.9 mg/kg after soybean cultivation. This final value is 14.8 mg/kg higher than the initial amount.

According to the data, in variants 1 and 2, where no forage crops were grown and maize and soybean were cultivated in the following year, the mobile phosphorus content in the 0–30 cm soil layer was 36.5 and 35.1 mg/kg, respectively, and decreased to 30.5 and 30.2 mg/kg by the end of the growing season.

In variants 3 and 4, where mustard and barley were used as forage crops, the initial values of mobile phosphorus in the 0–30 cm layer were 32.5 and 38.5 mg/kg, respectively, and increased to 38.4 and 39.5 mg/kg. This indicates that mustard has the ability to mobilize phosphorus in the soil through its root system. However, after soybean cultivation in the same variants, the amount of mobile phosphorus decreased to 36.2 mg/kg.

A similar pattern was observed in variants with two-, three-, and four-component forage crops. In variant 5, mobile phosphorus increased from 34.5 to 35.6 mg/kg, and then decreased to 34.2 mg/kg. In variant 6, it changed from 38.5 to 39.1 to 36.1 mg/kg; in variant 7 – from 34.6 to 38.2 to 32.1 mg/kg; and in variant 8 (four-component) – from 35.3 to 36.1 to 34.5 mg/kg.

In variants 1 and 2, where maize and soybean were grown as secondary crops, the initial exchangeable potassium content in the 0–30 cm soil layer was 351 and 343 mg/kg, respectively, and decreased to 304 and 308 mg/kg by the end of the season. This indicates that maize absorbs more nutrients, including potassium, compared to soybean.

In the variants where mustard and barley were grown as the first crops, the initial potassium values were 374 and 346 mg/kg, decreasing to 338 and 328 mg/kg by the end of the growing period, respectively. This suggests an imbalance in potassium within the soil-plant system.

In variants 5 and 6, where forage crops were sown as two- and three-component mixtures (triticale + rapeseed and triticale + rapeseed + vetch), the initial levels of exchangeable potassium were lower than in other variants. By the end of the growing period, these values decreased from 273–276 mg/kg to 256–296 mg/kg, and further dropped to 226–220 mg/kg by the end of the soybean growing period. Similar results were obtained in variants 7 and 8 with four-component mixtures (triticale + rapeseed + vetch + pea or triticale + rapeseed + pea + radish).

Thus, when forage crops and soybean are cultivated successively, the humus

content in the 0–30 cm soil layer increases from 1.103% to 1.116%, and after four types of intermediate crops, it increases from 1.145% to 1.165%. The total nitrogen content also increases from 0.121% to 0.141%.

Considering the growing need to include agricultural crops that leave more organic residues in the soil and help restore soil fertility in the cotton–grain short-rotation system, it is observed that the newly introduced rotation systems should be improved by integrating new types of repeated and intermediate crops.

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